

Nutrient Decision Support System (NuDSS) for irrigated rice

C. Witt, IRRI, Los Baños, Philippines;
A. Dobermann, University of Nebraska, Lincoln, USA; J. Arah, AAT Consultants, Edinburgh, UK; and R. Pamplona, IRRI
E-mail: c.witt@cgiar.org

The Nutrient Decision Support System (NuDSS) for irrigated rice is part of IRRI's initiative to provide decision support for site-specific nutrient management (SSNM) in the irrigated lowlands. The content of the software is consistent with printed information on SSNM provided by a field handbook (Dobermann and Fairhurst 2000) and a pocket guide (Fairhurst et al 2002). The NuDSS adds value to these materials by combining various models into one user-friendly software package to help users develop improved fertilizer strategies that aim at efficient fertilizer use and increased farmers' profit. The software was developed recognizing the need for decision aids providing assistance in complex mathematical calculations (e.g., through optimization routines) that would be difficult to perform otherwise.

Target audience and environment

The primary target audience of the NuDSS is intermediary technology transfer agents. The NuDSS can assist extension campaign planners from government or nongovernment organizations in the participatory development and validation of fertilizer strategies that are tailored to local conditions and farmers' needs. The software can also be used at the field scale, for example, assisting researchers in planning and evaluating experimental trials. Integrating agronomic and economic aspects of nutrient management makes NuDSS a powerful tool in teaching students.

The NuDSS is a generic decision support system for irrigated rice, capturing the most important cropping conditions in tropical and subtropical Asia. Guidelines for local adaptation are provided when conditions divert from standard situations. The underlying principles of plant nutrition are valid for all modern, high-yielding rice varieties with a harvest index of about 0.50 kg kg⁻¹. The model is currently also calibrated for wheat.

Content

The SSNM strategy in the NuDSS aims at achieving sustainable, large, and economic yields through proper nutrient management by

- Considering the differences in soil nutrient supply among sites (site-specific)
- Selecting reasonable yield goals (site- and season-specific)
- Making efficient use of all available nutrient sources including organic manures, crop residues, and inorganic fertilizers according to availability and costs
- Providing the crop with a balanced supply of nutrients (N, P, K, and micronutrients)
- Following plant-based N management using a leaf color chart (season-specific)
- Replacing nutrients, particularly P and K, removed with grain and straw to avoid depleting soil nutrient reserves

- Performing a gross margin analysis to obtain a profit estimate
- Performing cross-checks to reconsider developed strategies

The NuDSS is a Windows-based software that guides users step by step through the development of a fertilizer strategy. Figure 1 shows a flow chart of the various steps involved. The NuDSS requires a few input parameters that can be easily obtained at the farm level:

- Climate-adjusted yield potential of the variety used (season-specific)
- Current yield level in farmers' fields (season-specific)
- Current average fertilizer use in farmers' fields (season-specific)
- Plant-based estimates of indigenous soil N, P, and K supplies
- Available fertilizer sources including prices
- Costs of all inputs at the farm level for a gross margin analysis (optional)

Guidelines are provided to assist in the selection of default values where input parameters are not available. The NuDSS also provides suggestions for experimental layouts of on-farm validation trials to be used in farmer participatory evaluation of SSNM strategies. The NuDSS is complemented by IRRI's FarmMonitor, a database software for on-farm monitoring of agronomic and economic parameters measured at the field and farm levels.

Fig. 1. Flow chart of the nutrient decision support system for irrigated rice.

Graphical user interface and technology requirements

Operating screens with a minimum of text provide users with options for data entry or selection of default values before they are prompted to run optimization routines. A tutorial and background information on the principles of SSNM are provided in the Help function. The software has a built-in database for storing information such as default values (e.g., fertilizer sources, nutrient concentrations, prices, etc.) and developed fertilizer strategies. The NuDSS also provides the option for printing user-customized reports.

NuDSS 1.0 was programmed using Visual Basic 6.0 and MS Access. The accompanying database software FarmMonitor 1.0 was developed using Delphi 5.0 and MS Access. Both applications run under MS Windows 95/98/NT or Windows 2000 on a personal computer with at least 16-Mb RAM, a 66-mHz processor, a 100-Mb hard disk, and a CD-ROM. The NuDSS and FarmMonitor will be officially released by the end of 2001.

References

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PRICE: a decision support tool for the control of weeds in tropical irrigated rice

R.M. Wilkins, J.A. Garratt, and A.J. Laister, Department of Agricultural and Environmental Science, University of Newcastle Upon Tyne, UK
E-mail: richard.wilkins@ncl.ac.uk

Herbicide use is increasing in Asian rice production and is likely to continue in the near future. Direct seeding is also increasingly replacing transplanting as the dominant cropping system. There is a direct interaction between the availability of rice herbicides and the increase in use of direct-seeding technology. Direct seeding is viable in high-productivity irrigated systems if cost-effective herbicides are included in the control of weeds (Naylor 1996).

The past decade has seen a slow migration of labor from rural communities to the industrializing urban areas in Bangladesh, following a general trend across Asia. This has led to increasing labor costs, which have made direct seeding with the use of herbicides much more viable. Herbicide use is also favorable in transplanted rice. Research has shown a benefit-cost ratio of 16:1 (up to 25:1 with complete control) for the use of herbicides versus 3.3:1 for hand weeding (Naylor 1996). In Bangladesh, labor costs are as much as 44% of the variable costs of production (IRRI 1995). Herbicide use reduces costs in both direct-seeded and transplanted rice by reducing the cost of

labor for hand weeding. The use of direct seeding reduces labor costs further by eliminating the need for labor to maintain nurseries and transplant.

The major concern is how best to govern and regulate the use of rice herbicides as their use becomes more widespread. To do this, it is necessary to understand the effects of use on the population of the area, the effects of use on the environment, and the economic implications of usage or nonusage of herbicides.

Decision support systems and risk associated with increased herbicide use

The increased use of herbicides carries with it new risks. Herbicides may cause acute poisoning of workers or nontarget organisms. Residues may persist in soil and water, causing chronic health effects on both the ecosystem and humans. Rice plant vigor may be damaged if soil residues persist at phytotoxic levels until the next crop is established.

Decision support systems (DSS) provide a framework within which the severity of these risks can be evaluated along with the postulated yield and income benefits from herbicide use.

PRICE (Pesticide Residues in Irrigated Cereal Ecosystems) is a DSS that is partly data-driven and partly model-driven. It was developed to help determine environmentally acceptable and relevant herbicides for use in irrigated rice in the high-potential Indo-Gangetic plains of northern India and Bangladesh, but it is also useful in other tropical regions where irrigated rice is grown

